

Reliability Assessment of Pile-Founded Navigation Structures

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Abstract

The US Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) has designed pile-founded navigation structures to provide a consistently high level of safety and serviceability by using allowable values for pile stresses, pile load capacity, and deflections in structure design. Older in-service pile-founded navigation structures can be assessed using the same limit states used in the design of new pile-founded structures. This paper examines the reliability assessment of timber pile-founded navigation structures without the loss of support. The techniques developed to perform the reliability assessment employ a capacity/demand relationship for limit states of axial capacity, lateral deflections, axial deflections, and combined bending. Monte Carlo Simulations and First Order Second Moment techniques were used to calibrate the limit states to instrumented pile load test data from field tests. A river dam monolith subjected to impact loading is discussed herein.

Introduction

Traditionally, pile-founded navigation structures have been designed using allowable pile loads or pile stresses, or design has been controlled by use of structural deformations. Reliability analyses can utilize the same criteria used in the design of new pile foundations to assess older in-service pile-founded structures. While there are uncertainties as to design and construction, reasonable limits can usually be assigned to these variables based on available information. Thus, the uncertainties that are reflected in the reliability indices indicate the level of confidence that should be placed on the structure to perform its function.

The objective of this paper is to provide an introduction to the procedures discussed in the Corps of Engineers' Engineering Technical Letter (ETL) 1110-2-354 "Reliability Assessment of Pile-Founded Navigation Structures" [12]. The methodology used in ETL 1110-2-354 is intended to insure consistency and uniformity of

the procedures used to perform reliability assessments of pile-founded navigation structures to prioritize rehabilitation investments.

A pile-founded structure should be analyzed under the loading conditions to which it will be subjected during its life. Loading cases may be limited to controlling cases such as normal operation, maintenance (dewatered), extreme operation, or catastrophic events. A structural model should be developed that describes the important performance modes and limit states to be evaluated. Loads on the pile-founded structure may include lateral earth forces from soil adjacent to the structure, water loads from various pool levels, saturation in the backfill, uplift under the structure, ice loads, hawser pulls, and barge impact. The resistance of the structure can be accounted for by use of a horizontal subgrade reaction (with reductions for group and cyclic effects), axial and flexural capacity of the piles, and resisting forces such as weight of the structure and earth loads.

The model for a pile-founded navigation structure may be a cross section of the structure complete with loading diagram, stability analysis, and analyses of loads, stresses, or deflections in the piles. This may be accomplished by using the Corps of Engineers pile group analysis program, CPGA [5], which can analyze loading of pile groups in two or three dimensions. CPGA uses the stiffness method of pile group analysis introduced by Saul [9]. The program can be used to analyze steel, timber, and concrete piles including battered and unsupported piles.

Limit states for pile foundations

Limit states for pile-founded structures may be structural displacements (vertical and lateral), pile load capacity (axial and lateral), or pile stresses that result in unsatisfactory performance as the ratios of capacity (C) to demand (D) approach unity. Other performance modes for pile-founded structures not discussed in this paper

may include rotation of the pile head/pile cap and shear capacity of a pile. The limit states for pile foundations for this paper can be defined as follows:

1. Lateral and Vertical Deflections. Lateral and vertical deflections of the structure will be evaluated in terms of capacity divided by demand using the expression in which the limit state deflection is defined as movement that will result in unsatisfactory performance.

$$\frac{C}{D} = \frac{\text{LIMIT STATE DEFLECTION}}{\text{CALCULATED DEFLECTION}}$$

Pile-supported structures may be evaluated in terms of calculated deflections compared to a limit that could result in unsatisfactory performance. For a navigation structure, limit state deflections would be those that may cause operational problems with gates or machinery, unacceptable misalignment of concrete surfaces, concrete cracking, or rupture of waterstops. Because small rotations or translations of pile caps can result in unacceptably large movements at the structure crest, magnification of pile deformations due to structure height and base dimensions should be taken into account in setting values for limit state deformations.

2. Axial Capacity of Piles. Axial loads on the piling are evaluated in terms of pile capacity in compression (AC) divided by axial compression load on the piles (F3)

$$C/D = AC/F3$$

and the expression for tension piles with the tensile load capacity (AT)

$$C/D = AT/ABS(-F3)$$

The limit state axial and lateral loads can be taken as pile loads that produce maximum acceptable pile deformations which will depend on the type of structure. If load tests are not available, pile capacities may be calculated in accordance with Engineering Manual (EM) 1110-2-2906 [10].

3. Pile Stresses (Combined bending). Stresses in the piling will be evaluated in terms of the interaction equation for a compression pile

$$\frac{C}{D} = \frac{1}{\frac{F3}{ACC} + \frac{M1}{AM1} + \frac{M2}{AM2}}$$

and the expression for tension piles as

$$\frac{C}{D} = \frac{1}{\frac{ABS(-F3)}{ATT} + \frac{M1}{AM1} + \frac{M2}{AM2}}$$

where:

F3 = axial compressive load in the pile

-F3 = axial tensile load in the pile

ACC = limit state yield compressive load

ATT = limit state yield tensile load

M1, M2 = bending moment in the pile about axis 1 and 2

AM1, AM2 = limit state yield bending moment in the pile about axis 1 and 2

The pile stresses of primary interest for steel and timber piling are axial and flexural compression. For prestressed concrete and particularly reinforced concrete, axial tension and flexural tension may control. The critical location is at the pile cap for fixed-head piles and at a point near maximum moment for pinned piles.

Calibration

Pile tests were conducted from April to October 1978 on Ellis Island, near Alton, Illinois, and just downstream from Old Lock and Dam 26 (L&D 26) on the Mississippi River [7]. The tests were designed to evaluate the existing pile-supported dam and alternative construction techniques to rehabilitate the dam. Single piles and pile groups of eight and twelve piles were instrumented and tested to determine the ultimate load capacities of the piles and pile groups and the effects of cyclic loading on deflections of the dam at the extreme operating load level. As the loads on the pile groups simulated normal service conditions, extreme operating conditions, and severe overload conditions, Monolith M2 from those tests was evaluated and calibrated as a pile-supported dam to test the reliability assessment methods previously described.

Reliability analyses of Monolith M2

Monolith M2 is one of seven monoliths constructed for the series of tests on Ellis Island. Monolith M2 is supported on eight timber piles arranged in two rows of four piles on 3-ft centers each way as shown in Figure 1. The piles, with a 14-in. minimum diameter at the butt and the concrete monolith, were instrumented to measure strains and deformations. Size and spacing of piles were

selected to simulate the design of the existing dam at old L&D 26.

Figure 1 Layout of Monolith M2

Monolith M2 was constructed and loaded to simulate the pile foundation for existing L&D 26. The reliability of Monolith M2 was assessed at two levels of lateral loading, 12 kips per pile, which is representative of an extreme operating condition or maintenance condition, and 24 kips per pile, which represents a limit state condition of imminent distress. Deflections of M2 under the 12 kips per pile loading were measured at a lateral deflection of 0.7 in. For the 24 kips per pile loading, the measured deflection was 2.1 in. While the pile group was able to withstand a 30 kips-per-pile lateral load (without failure), the lateral deflections were 5.1 inches which more than doubled that for the 24 kips per pile loading. Vertical loads of 60 kips per pile were maintained for both lateral loads. These applied lateral and vertical loads are known with reasonable certainty and will be treated as constants.

The axial load capacity of the eight piles in M2 was estimated using a pile driving analyzer under restrike conditions two or three days after initial driving. A mean axial capacity of 141.56 kips per pile with a standard deviation of 18.6 kips per pile was determined. This compares well with the axial capacity of the single pile group, Monolith M6, which also had an axial capacity of 140 kips. These values can also be checked by using the method presented in EM 1110-2-2906 and the Corps of Engineers computer program, CAXPILE [6]. Using a measured internal friction angle of 40 deg and a saturated unit weight of 130 pcf, the procedure in EM 1110-2-2906 estimates the mean axial capacity at 138 kips, whereas CAXPILE estimates the ultimate capacity of the piles at approximately 150 kips. A mean

axial capacity of 140 kips with a standard deviation of 14 kips was used.

The axial stiffness term, b_{33} in the stiffness matrix can be expressed as $b_{33} = C_{33} (AE/L)$, where C_{33} is the axial stiffness modifier. The values used in this analysis for C_{33} for monolith M2 are determined from the actual settlement at the center of the monolith that occurred during lateral loading. Settlement at a lateral load of 12 kips per pile was 0.25 in., which yields a C_{33} value of 0.46. Settlement that occurred at 24 kips per pile was 0.4 in. which predicts a C_{33} value of 0.28. Analyses using these values for C_{33} will accurately reflect vertical, lateral, and rotational displacements of the M2 pile cap measured in the pile tests.

The size of piling used in the Ellis Island load tests was not well documented. Perez and Holloway [7] indicate only that "Fourteen-inch butt diameter timber piles were jetted and driven at 3 feet on center." It is assumed that the piles varied in size but would have met a subsequent ASTM Specification D25-91 [1], which requires that no more than 10 percent of the piles have a circumference less than 44 in., and that none has a circumference less than 42 in. Assuming that pile sizes are normally distributed, a mean pile diameter of 14.3 in. and a standard deviation of 0.23 in. would be expected.

The test piling used at Ellis Island was a douglas fir (coast type) species. The ultimate flexural strength of this material as determined by the average modulus of rupture of small clear specimens is given in ASTM Specification D2555 [2] as 7,665 psi, with a standard deviation of 1,317 psi. The limit state yield was taken as 75 percent of these values, or $F_b = 5,749$ psi with a standard deviation of 988 psi. The ultimate compressive strength of coast douglas fir as determined by the average crushing strength of small clear specimens tested parallel to the grain is given in ASTM Specification D2555 [2] as 3,784 psi with a standard deviation of 734 psi. The limit state yield will be taken as 75 percent of these values or $F_c = 2,838$ psi with a standard deviation of 551 psi.

Bending moments and shears in the piling were determined from strain gauges placed on the piling. Analysis was performed to determine the constant of horizontal subgrade reaction, n_h , to duplicate the measured shears, positive and negative moments, and pile head displacements along the piling using the Corps of Engineers computer program CBEAMC [4], which permits the use of a spring constant to model the horizontal subgrade reaction for each individual pile. The results of this determination of n_h for six instrumented piles under Monoliths M2 and M1 are discussed in Ref [12]. The values used for n_h in the analysis for the 12 kips per pile load were 34.2 pci with a standard deviation of 8.5 pci

and, for the 24 kips per pile load were 21.2 pci with a standard deviation of 5.5 pci.

The performance modes analyzed for this structure were for lateral and vertical deflections, pile stresses, and axial pile loads. For a gated dam, the limit state deflection may be taken as the maximum tolerable movement that would not cause the gate to bind or machinery to become misaligned. EM 1110-2-2906 limits new pile foundation designs to 1/2 in. lateral deflection and 1/4 in. in vertical deflections. These values may seem too limited, so in lieu of detailed structural data and for example purposes in this paper, the limit state lateral deflection for M2 was assigned a value of 1 in. lateral deflection and 3/8 in. vertical deflection for both the 12 and 24 kips per pile lateral loadings.

Reliability Results

A First Order Second Moment Taylor's Series Finite Difference Method (FOSM-TSFD) as described in ETL 1110-2-532 [11] and Monte Carlo Simulations were used to evaluate the reliability of M2 for the 12 and 24 kips per pile loadings. Table 1 shows the results.

1. Extreme operating condition, 12 kips per pile lateral load. The lateral load of 12 kips for a timber pile is appropriately designated an extreme operating condition. Reliability indices of $\beta = 4.083$ for pile stresses, and $\beta = 3.974$ for axial loads are reasonable for pile-supported structures subjected to this level of loading. A slightly lower value of $\beta = 3.50$ could be tolerated for extreme operating conditions and slightly higher indices would be expected for normal operating conditions. Engineering judgment and a knowledge of the structure are necessary to set a reasonable limit state deflection. A limit state value of 1.00 in. lateral and 0.375 in. vertical displacements selected without a detailed knowledge of the structure resulted in reliability indices of $\beta = 3.02$ for lateral deflections and $\beta = >4.00$ for vertical deflections. These values should be taken as a demonstration of procedure and not a true evaluation of the simulated dam.

2. Conditions of overstress, 24 kips per pile. Calculated reliability indices $\beta = -0.084$ for pile stresses and $\beta = 0.823$ for axial loads clearly indicate a high probability of unsatisfactory performance consistent with observations of the test. Using a limit state value of 1 in. lateral and 0.375 in. vertical displacements resulted in reliability indices of $\beta = < -4.00$ lateral and $\beta = -2.198$ vertical. The values for a negative reliability index which would yield a probability of unsatisfactory performance of

$P(u) \sim 1$ should be taken as a demonstration of the procedure and not a true evaluation of the simulated dam.

Table 1 Reliability Results for Ellis Island

	Extreme Operating Level	Overstress Level
	12 kips per pile	24 kips per pile
Pile Stresses	4.083	-0.084
Axial Capacity	3.974	0.823
Lateral Deflection	3.473	<-4.00
Vertical Deflection	>4.00	-2.198

Example Application

This example application is taken from analyses of the pile-supported fixed-crest dam at Locks and Dam No. 2 on the Monongahela River. The concrete gravity dam was constructed in 1903 and is supported on five rows of vertical timber piles, which are southern pine with a 12-in. minimum butt diameter. The piles are spaced at 4 ft., 3 in. in each direction, are embedded 3 ft. into the concrete, and are assumed to have full moment fixity. The piles were driven either to refusal in dense sand overlying rock or to bearing on rock 30 ft below the base of the dam. Wakefield timber piling used as a seepage barrier is located at the upstream and downstream ends of the concrete structure. No vertical or lateral support from these cutoff walls has been assumed. A sixth row of timber piles is located against the upstream face of the dam but appears to offer no support to the dam. This piling is presumed to be a part of temporary shoring used for construction that was left in place. The dam was threatened by scour that undermined and damaged stone-filled timber cribbing placed against the downstream toe of the dam. This example evaluates the dam in its scoured condition without the cribbing. Figure 2 shows a cross section of the dam.

Reliability Analysis of Dam 2

1. Pool levels. Preliminary analyses indicate that a pool combination of upper pool el 722.7 ft and lower pool el 712 ft produced the maximum load on the foundation. These conditions can be expected when the flow in the river is in the range of 20,000 cfs, which is a common occurrence. Because this combination of pools is reasonably certain to occur frequently, the resulting load will be treated as a constant. The lateral pressure exerted by the tailwater was reduced by 40 percent to account for the dynamic effects of flowing water.

and must be reduced for group and cyclic effects. The group reduction factor, R_g , was determined for the spacing of the piles which was 4 ft., 3 in. in both directions (4.25 ft.) and a pile diameter of 12.39 in.. This yields a mean group reduction factor of R_g of 2.3 with a coefficient of variation of 10 percent. The cyclic reduction factor, R_c , was estimated with a mean value of 2.0 with a 25 percent coefficient of variation.

The First Order Second Moment Taylor's Series method (FOSM-TSFD) described in ETL 1110-2-532 and Monte Carlo Simulations were used to evaluate the reliability of Dam 2 for the normal operating condition and the normal operating condition with impact. For this example, the limit state lateral deflection has been assigned a value of 3/4 in. lateral deflection and 1/4 in. vertical deflection. Table 2 shows a summary and comparison of the reliabilities for Monongahela River Dam No. 2 for both normal operating and normal operating with impact.

Reliability Results

1. Normal operating condition The expected performance level of Dam 2 under normal conditions is high, as indicated by a reliability index $\beta = 6.05$ for the mode of pile stresses and $\beta = 5.02$ for the mode of pile loads, and $\beta = 3.699$ and 3.984 for the modes of lateral and vertical deflections, respectively. The dam was calculated to deflect 0.476 in. laterally under normal loading conditions.

2. Normal operating condition with impact. The expected performance level of Dam 2 under normal loads and impact is below average, as indicated by a reliability index $\beta = 2.652$ for the mode of pile stresses. The reliability index, β , for the mode of pile loads was only slightly lower at 2.471. The reliability indices for the modes of lateral and vertical deflections were $\beta = 0.273$ and $\beta = 2.176$, respectively. While the dam has performed satisfactorily to date, there is an element of risk involving barge impacts that may exceed those that have occurred in the past. Deflection under normal loading condition with impact was calculated to be 0.71 in.

Acknowledgments

The author would like to acknowledge the funding of this study through the Civil Works Risk Research and Development Program. The author would also like to thank Dr. Mary Ann Leggett and Dr. Reed L. Mosher, USACE Waterways Experiment Station for their assistance, guidance, and support during this research effort. Permission was granted by the Chief of Engineers

to publish this information. The views of the author do not purport to reflect the position of the Department of the Army or Department of Defense.

Table 2 Reliability Results - Dam No. 2

	<u>Normal</u>	<u>Normal with Impact</u>
Pile Stresses	>4	2.652
Axial Capacity	>4	2.471
Lateral Deflection	3.699	0.273
Vertical Deflection	3.984	2.176

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